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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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April M. Bagon-Faeldan

Associate Professor III

Mindoro State University

Main Campus

Victoria, Oriental Mindoro, Philippines

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The Quiet Kindness: A Plea for Respect in Public Spaces

“Consideration for the rights and feelings of others is not merely a rule for behavior in public but the very foundation upon which social life is built.”

- Emily Post

The Bird’s-Eye View

This essay reflects that fellow travelers and passengers in all public places should practice respect. In a busy, digital world, public places served as shared ground for different people in different walks of life. Buses, ships, airports, and terminals are places where people stop for a while to wait for their travel different places. Yet, in these shared spaces, a simple truth is often forgotten and neglected: we are not alone. The way we act in public shows not only who we are but also how much we value others.

An Annoying Experience in Public Places

“Tumatanda ka na kasi!” (You are getting older!) This is a jest I commonly heard from my friend Vina whenever I rant about the noise of people watching reels on their smartphones and talking too loudly in public places like bus terminals, port terminals, and the like.

As a frequent traveler from the island of Oriental Mindoro, I have come to know the long journey that many island residents must take. I started travelling from our province to Batangas in Manila when I enrolled in the graduate programs. To reach Manila, one must first endure a boat ride of one and a half to three hours to Batangas, followed by another two to three hours by land. This journey is really tiring, and for many passengers, travel time is also rest time. However, this much-needed peace is often broken by those who seem unaware of the people around them. This is the time I easily get irritated.

One of the most common problems I have noticed is the loud playing of short videos or reels on smartphones. This easily annoys me. I hate the sounds of noise while on travel. Many unconscious passengers watch comedy clips, lifestyle content, and confession videos without using headphones. The sounds fill the cabin and make it hard for others to rest or think. I often judged them as selfish human being. These people believe that they are just along in their living room or resting place rather than in a shared public space. A simple pair of earphones would solve this problem, yet many choose not to use them. I often associate

this with lack of considerations. Mostly, old people are doing this. This lack of awareness is not just rude; it shows a failure to recognize that other people also have needs.

I always approach them in my pleading voice “ Pwede pong pakihinaan ang volume ng inyong pinapanood? Nais ko rin pong magpahinga habang nasa byahe..” [Could you please lower the volume of the videos you are watching? I want to rest while on travel...]. Most people have positive response towards this request. But there are some who is inconsiderate and I must say heartless. At this time, I always being with me my portable speaker, play an annoying music. I wanted them to feel how annoying their habit was.

Another issue is loud talking, whether in person or on the phone. Some passengers speak as though everyone around them wants to hear their conversation. They laugh loudly, shout into their phones, and carry on as if the bus or boat were their private space. I heard a lot of stories. A story of teenage pregnancy, rants about their bosses, delayed salaries, family problems, and many more. I keep on asking, “Why do I or we need to hear those stories?” “Why do these people don’t have *kahihiyang*?”

At this juncture, I wanted to ask: Are we not concerned that some people need quiet? Are we not aware that others may be tired, unwell, or simply in need of peace? A little care in lowering our voices can go a long way in making public travel more pleasant for everyone.

The behavior of children in public places is another matter that deserves attention. Yes, children will be children. They laugh, cry, and move about. However, there is a clear difference between children who are taught to behave in public and those who are not. Some parents take the time to train their children to speak softly, stay seated, and respect the space of others. Other parents seem to let their children do as they please, no matter how much noise or trouble they cause. While we must always be patient with young ones, parents also have a duty to teach their children that public spaces require a different kind of behavior than home.

A Call to Action: A Respect in Public Places

Respect in public places is not about strict rules or harsh judgment. It is about kindness. A little consideration. An empathy. It is about remembering that the person sitting next to you may have woken up early, may be going through a hard time, or may simply need a moment of calm. When we lower our voices, use headphones, and teach our children to be mindful, we are saying to others: I see you, and I care about your comfort too. This is the quiet kindness that makes life in society bearable and even beautiful.

In buses, terminals, ports, and airports, we share not just space but also moments of our lives. Let us make those moments easier for one another. Let us show empathy. Let us put on our headphones or headsets before playing a video. Let us speak softly on our phones. Let us guide our children to be respectful of others. These small acts cost us nothing; they are really free, and yet they give so much to those around us. In the end, respect in public places is not a burden. It is a gift we give to strangers, and in doing so, we make our shared world a kinder place to live.